

Norfloxacin-Tinidazole Induced Stevens-Johnson Syndrome in Elderly Diabetic Patient: A Case Report

M. Nisar Ahamed*¹, Thrishnitha Dasari², Chigullapally Sai Priya²

¹Assistant Professor, Sri Venkateshwara College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, India

²Pharm D Students, Sri Venkateshwara College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, India

ABSTRACT

Stevens-Johnson Syndrome (SJS) is an acute severe, uncommon, and potentially life-threatening condition involving skin and mucous membrane. Its global incidence is estimated at 0.05 to 2 individuals per million people annually. SJS is a serious hypersensitivity reaction that can occur due to infections or as a side effect of drugs (Anticonvulsants, Antibiotics, NSAIDs). Fluoroquinolones are broad spectrum antibiotics with wide range of activity used to treat respiratory tract, gastrointestinal and genitourinary infections. Fluoroquinolones, broad-spectrum antibiotics such as Norfloxacin is reported to rarely associated in inducing SJS (0.01% to 0.1%). Nitroimidazoles such as Tinidazole could exacerbate SJS when used concurrently with fluoroquinolones (FQs). In this case, a 66-year old diabetic and hypertensive female of Indian nationality presented with complaints of rashes, multiple blisters over legs, hands and swollen lips for the past 3 days. Patient was prescribed with antibiotic Norflox-TZ (a combination of Norfloxacin and Tinidazole) for loose stools and fever. After 48 hours of twice a day consumption she developed rashes, associated with blisters. Therefore, it was suspected that fluoroquinolone along with nitroimidazole could be the possible causative agent in our case. Based on the Naranjo's causality scale, the reaction was assessed as 'probable' fluoroquinolone along with nitroimidazole induced SJS. The patient recovered after withdrawal of suspected drug and appropriate management, including systemic corticosteroids, topical applications and medications for her comorbid conditions. After full recovery, the patient was discharged in a stable condition. This case highlights the critical role of pharmacists in identifying, preventing and managing adverse drug reactions through vigilant monitoring and their intensive knowledge in medications.

Keywords: Stevens-Johnson syndrome, Toxic epidermal necrolysis, Vesiculobullous.

INTRODUCTION

Stevens-Johnson Syndrome and Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN) are acute severe, uncommon, but potentially life-threatening skin conditions characterized by skin loss and, in some instances, mucosal membrane is also involved. Systemic manifestations are also reported in few cases. Stevens-Johnson Syndrome (SJS) is an inflammatory vesiculobullous reaction of the skin, the mucosa of the ocular surface, the oral cavity, and of the genitals; whereas its severe type is called Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN). [1] Stevens-Johnson Syndrome/Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis is estimated to occur in 0.05 to 2 individuals per million people in a year globally. [2,3] Mortality rates range from 4.8-9% to 14.8-48%, with females being more commonly

affected than males. SJS is considered as delayed type hypersensitivity reactions to medications. Over 80% of cases are caused by medications like anticonvulsants (Phenytoin), Allopurinol, sulfonamides, antibiotics (penicillins, cephalosporins), nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs derived from propionic acid (e.g., ibuprofen) etc. Genetic factors, such as specific human leukocyte antigen (HLA) allotypes, can increase the risk of developing Stevens-Johnson Syndrome/Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis when exposed to aromatic anticonvulsants and allopurinol.[4] Fluoroquinolones (FQ's) are classified as broad-spectrum antibiotics, commonly prescribed for treating infections in the genitourinary, respiratory, gastrointestinal, skin, and soft tissue areas.[5] Tinidazole is a nitroimidazole

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

class of drug. It is commonly used as an antibiotic and antiprotozoal medication to treat various infections, caused by bacteria and protozoa. These antibiotics are typically well tolerated, with fewer than 5% of patients requiring to discontinue treatment due to side effects. Stevens-Johnson Syndrome (SJS) and Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN) have been associated with fluoroquinolones and nitroimidazole, although these occurrences are very rare. Fixed drug combination eruptions are localized skin reactions that appear at the same site upon repeated exposure to the drug, and they may occur in some individuals. These types of reactions are consistent with usage of fluoroquinolones along with nitroimidazole.[6]

CASE REPORT:

A 66-year-old post-menopausal female was presented with chief complaints of rashes, multiple blisters over legs, hands and swelling of her lips since 3 days. Patient had history of abdominal pain associated with multiple episodes of loose stools, fever, body aches for the past 5 days. The patient was prescribed with Tab.Paracetamol for body pains, Tab.Lomotil for loose stools and antibiotic Tab. Norflox-TZ in other medical facility, after 48 hours of Norflox-TZ twice a day consumption she developed rashes, associated with blisters. During present admission, she was conscious, oriented, cooperative. Her temperature was 98°F, pulse was 79beats/minute, respiratory rate was 20breaths/minute, blood pressure was 110/80 mmHg and her random blood sugar level was 250mg/dl. Her medical history revealed that she had type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension, choriocarcinoma, status post chemotherapy. Patient is on medication for comorbid conditions, includes Pantoprazole (PAN) 40mg, Glimepiride in combination with Metformin (Zoryl M2) for diabetes, Cilnidipine in combination with Telmisartan (Cinod-T) for hypertension, Rosuvastatin for dyslipidemia (Rozavel) 10mg, Pregabalin and Methyl Cobalamin (Pregator- M) 75mg, Inj Apidra (Insulin glulisine) 10units to control blood glucose levels.

On evaluation investigations showed TSH within normal limits, RFT (Renal function test) within normal limits, serum electrolytes within normal limits sodium: 140, potassium: 4.2, Hb- 12.2, ALP-139, ALT-54, HbA1c- 6.7%, CRP-9.63, ESR-70.93, Blood

urea nitrogen-12 mg/dl, Serum glucose- 248mg/dl, Bicarbonate level- 23 mmol/L, Albumin-globulin ratio: 0.9.2 DECHO with colour doppler demonstrated normal sized cardiac chambers with no LV Regional wall motion abnormality, LVEF: 60%, Urine culture showed no growth. Gastrointestinal panel detected presence of E. coli. The patient had history of rash in the past but not associated with blisters subsided with antihistamines. Present reaction occurred after introduction of Norflox-TZ but not due to usage of long-term medications. The final diagnosis concluded by clinician was Norflox-TZ induced Stevens Johnson Syndrome. After diagnosis of SJS, Tab. Norflox-TZ was stopped and treated with steroids, antihistamines.

DISCUSSION:

Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) are a major cause of illness and death. In India, approximately 2.9% to 5.6% of hospital admissions are attributed to ADRs.[7] SJS is a rare and severe cutaneous ADR which requires hospitalization. According to the involvement of body surface area (BSA), the disease can be classified into SJS (30% BSA) and SJS-TEN overlaps (10%- 30% BSA).[8] Approximately 40% of drug-induced Stevens-Johnson Syndrome (SJS) cases are associated with antibiotics. Fluoroquinolones (FQ), such as Ciprofloxacin (less than 0.01%) and Norfloxacin (0.01% to 0.1%) rarely cause drug-induced SJS.[9] Norfloxacin, a Fluoroquinolone derivative, is a broad-spectrum antibiotic commonly used to treat urinary and respiratory tract infections. It has an extensive antimicrobial spectrum, covering a wide range of gram negative and gram-positive organisms. In such case, it's possible that Tinidazole could exacerbate SJS when used in conjunction with fluoroquinolones (FQs).[10] In this condition, blisters begin to form on the skin, which then spread, causing the skin to peel or shed, eventually leading to the death of the affected skin. This occurs due to an overly active immune response, which triggers severe inflammation. This process involves various components of the immune system, including MHC-1, T-helper cells, cytokines, neutrophils, macrophages, CD-8+ T cells, and other elements of the innate immune system. Variations in the HLA-B gene can cause abnormal immune reactions to certain medications that are likely to

trigger Stevens-Johnson syndrome (SJS). Drug-induced cytotoxic T cells and natural killer cells produce granulysin, which destroys skin and mucosal cells due to the body's inability to eliminate reactive metabolites. Diagnosis is primarily based on clinical symptoms and the histopathological examination of skin lesions. This condition typically begins with flu-like symptoms followed by red or purple rashes that spread to form blisters and also leads to high fever, tiredness, fatigue, sore throat, mouth ulcers. This requires immediate medical attention. A skin specialist typically diagnoses it by evaluating a combination of the patient's symptoms, medical history (both past and present), and physical examination.[11]

Recent advances in SJS/TEN management focus on immunomodulatory therapies alongside supportive care. Cyclosporine (3–5 mg/kg/day) can reduce mortality by inhibiting T-cell-mediated keratinocyte apoptosis. TNF α inhibitors like etanercept or adalimumab, sometimes combined with

corticosteroids, may accelerate healing and decrease mortality. IVIG has been used, though its benefit is inconsistent, and plasmapheresis is explored for refractory cases. These treatments are adjuncts and should be used alongside comprehensive supportive care and the prompt discontinuation of the offending medication, rather than as a substitute.[12]

NARANJO'S ALGORITHM:

In this case, Naranjo's algorithm was applied to assess the likelihood of a reaction caused by Norfloxacin-Tinidazole.[13] Based on naranjo's algorithm, the total score was 8 (Table:1), this Stevens-Johnson Syndrome (SJS) was classified as a "probable" reaction to Norfloxacin-Tinidazole administration. Such adverse event has been previously reported which provides evidence that this is a probable reaction and with further dermatologist consultation reconfirmed it as Norfloxacin TZ induced Stevens-Johnson Syndrome.

Table:1 Naranjo's Algorithm

Question	Yes	No	Don't know	Score
1. Are there previous conclusive reports on this reaction?	+1	0	0	1
2. Did the adverse event appear after the suspected drug was administered?	+2	-1	0	2
3. Did the adverse event improve when the drug was discontinued, or a specific antagonist was administered?	+1	0	0	1
4. Did the adverse event reappear when the drug was readministered?	+2	-1	0	0
5. Are there alternative causes that could on their own have caused the reaction?	-1	+2	0	2
6. Did the reaction reappear when a placebo was given?	-1	+1	0	0
7. Was the drug detected in blood or other fluids in concentration known to be toxic?	+1	0	0	0
8. Was the reaction more severe when the dose was increased or less severe when the dose was decreased?	+1	0	0	0
9. Did the patient have a similar reaction to the same or similar drugs in any previous exposure?	+1	0	0	1
10. Was the adverse event confirmed by any objective evidence?	+1	0	0	1

In India, guidelines are available for management of SJS which recommend immediate withdrawal of all suspected drugs along with adequate supportive treatment. If patients of SJS have been identified at a primary or secondary healthcare facility, the treatment should be initialized prior to their referral to a tertiary care centre.[14] Preventive measures against infection

include maintaining hygiene, caring for wounds, replenishing lost fluids and nutrients, and providing eye care. The approach also focuses on symptomatic management and improvement through the use of general pain relievers, antibiotics, and other medications tailored to the patient's needs, which helps prevent potential complications.

A validated scoring system known as the “Severity-of-Illness Score for Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (SCORTEN)” has been established to help predict the prognosis and outcome in patients with Stevens–Johnson Syndrome (SJS) and Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis (TEN). The SCORTEN index includes seven independent predictors of mortality [Table 2]. Each factor is assigned a score of one point, and the total SCORTEN is determined by adding up the number of abnormal parameters.

Table 2: SCORTEN- severity- of-illness score for Toxic epidermal Necrolysis [15]

Prognostic parameters in the severity- of-illness score for Toxic epidermal Necrolysis [SCORTEN]
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age > 40 years • Presence of malignancy • Tachycardia (heart rate above 120 beats/min) • Initial percentage of epidermal detachment > 10% • Blood urea Nitrogen > 28mg/dl • Serum glucose > 252mg/dl • Bicarbonate level < 20 mmol/L

According to the SCORTEN scale, the patient meets two clinical parameters, which corresponds to an estimated mortality risk of approximately 12%. Patient was given with intravenous fluids (IV NS 70ml/hr) for hydration, systemic administration of corticosteroids (Solumedrol), Empirical antibiotic (Zostum 1.5g), antihypertensives (Cilnidipine 10mg twice a day, Telmisartan 40mg was later added for breakthrough spikes in BP), pain management (Pregabalin 75mg). SJS symptoms treated with Inj.Avil 22.75mg, Inj.Hydrocort 100mg, topical application of Fusidic acid cream for rashes. In hospital patient developed rashes all over the face upon administration of Inj.Zostum 1.5g, no new blisters found and the drug was withdrawn. This shows patient is hypersensitive to other drugs also apart from Norflox-TZ. Further, topical therapy with Mupirocin Ointment was prescribed for rashes. The patient recovered and was discharged after 4 days of treatment. Since the gastrointestinal panel confirmed presence of E. coli, Inflammatory bowel disease is also suspected which needs further evaluation. The discharge medications included Rabeprazole 20mg OD, Prednisolone 20mg OD for 7 days, Fusidic acid over the rash OD, Telmisartan 40mg OD, Pregaba M

75mg OD, Rosuvastatin 10mg OD, Mupirocin ointment as a topical applicant BD, Inj Apidra (Insulin glulisine) 10units TID for diabetes mellitus type-2 and adjust the dosage management according to blood glucose levels. Patient was educated to avoid any quinolone group of antibiotics, Tinidazole, Metronidazole and Ornidazole. Follow up was scheduled after 7 days.

CONCLUSION:

The incidence of SJS associated with Norfloxacin and Tinidazole is very uncommon. We encountered a patient who was diagnosed with Norfloxacin-Tinidazole induced SJS. The patient was having comorbid conditions such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension. She recovered completely after withdrawing the drug in addition to treatment with other symptomatic measures. Generally, use of medications that can potentially cause SJS requires careful monitoring. Patients should be educated to observe and report any adverse reactions (ADR's) encountered with the use of such medications. SJS is very rare and early identification, management is necessary to prevent detrimental outcomes.

Challenges faced in this case:

Identifying the offending drug was challenging, as the patient presented with overlapping symptoms from multiple medications, and Tinidazole itself is not commonly associated with causing Stevens–Johnson Syndrome (SJS), making causality assessment more complex. The second antibiotic, Cefoperazone–Sulbactam (1.5 g), also induced dermatological rashes, indicating that the patient was hypersensitive to multiple antibiotics. The reaction resolved following discontinuation of the drug and initiation of topical therapy for the rashes.

Role of Clinical Pharmacist in Identifying, Preventing and Managing Adverse Reactions:

Pharmacists play an important role in identification, and prevention as well as management of ADRs.[16] The role of pharmacists is crucial due to their extensive knowledge of medications. Pharmacists are responsible for promoting the maintenance, development, and continuous evaluation of programs aimed at minimizing the risks of adverse drug

reactions (ADRs).[17] Reporting ADRs is an essential component in monitoring and evaluating the activities performed in hospitals. A hospital-based reporting program provides valuable insights into medication-related issues within the healthcare facility. By identifying and addressing these problems, patient care can be enhanced. Pharmacists play an important role in educating patients about medications and their potential adverse effects is crucial for preventing such reactions. Patient medicals records should be properly flagged for proven allergies to avoid further adverse reactions.

REFERENCE

1. Ueta M. Pathogenesis of Stevens-Johnson Syndrome/toxic epidermal necrolysis with severe ocular complications. *Frontiers Med.* 2021;8.
2. Li LF, Ma C. Epidemiological study of severe cutaneous adverse drug reactions in a city district in China. *Clin Exp Dermatol.* 2006;31: 642–7.
3. Borchers AT, Lee JL, Naguwa SM, Cheema GS, Gershwin ME. Stevens-Johnson syndrome and toxic epidermal necrolysis. *Autoimmun Rev.* 2008; 7: 598-605.
4. Wolf R, Marinović B. Drug eruptions in the mature patient. *Clin Dermatol.* 2018 Mar-Apr;36(2):249-254. [PubMed]
5. Goldstein EJ. Norfloxacin, (1987). a fluoroquinolone antibacterial agent. Classification, mechanism of action, and in vitro activity. *Am J Med,* 82(6):3-17.
6. Mehsas Z, Boubnane I, Sektaoui S, Meziane M, Ismaili N et.al. (2013). DRESS syndrome: A descriptive series of 62 cases. *Our Dermatology Online/Nasza Dermatologia Online,* 14(3).
7. Jonklaas J, Bianco AC, Bauer AJ, et al. (2014). Guidelines for the treatment of hypothyroidism: prepared by the American Thyroid Association Task Force on Thyroid Hormone Replacement. *Thyroid,* 24:1670-1751
8. Kumar R, Das A, Das S. Management of Stevens-Johnson syndrome-toxic epidermal necrolysis: looking beyond guidelines! *Indian J Dermatol.* 2018;63(2):117–24.
9. Abulatan I T, Ben-David S G, Morales-Colon L A, et al. (November 13, 2023) A Compilation of Drug Etiologies of Stevens-Johnson Syndrome and Toxic Epidermal Necrolysis. *Cureus* 15(11): e48728. DOI 10.7759/cureus.
10. Hennessey JV. The emergence of levothyroxine as a treatment for hypothyroidism. *Endocrine.* 2017;55:6–18
11. Website, N. (2024, June 13). Stevens-Johnson syndrome. [nhs.uk. https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/stevens-johnson-syndrome/](https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/stevens-johnson-syndrome/)
12. Yao, L., et al. (2025). Recent developments in the research of Stevens-Johnson syndrome and toxic epidermal necrolysis. *European Journal of Medical Research,* 30(1), 1-10.
13. Naranjo CA, Busto U, Sellers EM, Sandor P, Ruiz I, Roberts EA, Janecek E, et al. (1981). A method for estimating the probability of adverse drug reactions. *Clin Pharmacol Ther,* 30:239- 245.
14. Gupta LK, Martin AM, Agarwal N, D□Souza P, Das S, Kumar R, Pande S, Das NK, Kumaresan M, Kumar P, Garg A, Singh S. Guidelines for the management of Stevens–Johnson syndrome/toxic epidermal necrolysis: An Indian perspective. *Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol* 2016;82:603-625
15. Bastuji-Garin S, Fouchard N, Bertocchi M, Roujeau JC, Revuz J, Wolkenstein P. SCORTEN: A severity-of-illness score for toxic epidermal necrolysis. *J Invest Dermatol* 2000;115:149-53.
16. Bushra R, Baloch SA, Jabeen A, Bano N, Aslam N. Adverse drug reactions (ADRs): factors and role of pharmacist in their prevention. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad.* 2015;27:702–6.
17. Howard RL, Avery AJ, Howard PD, Patridge M. Investigation in to the reasons for preventable drug admissions to a medical admissions unit: observational study. *Qual Saf Health Care.* 2003;12:280–5. [https://doi.org/10.1136/qhc.12.4.280.](https://doi.org/10.1136/qhc.12.4.280)

HOW TO CITE: M. Nisar Ahamed, Thrishnitha Dasari, Chigullapally Sai Priya, Norfloxacin-Tinidazole Induced Stevens-Johnson Syndrome in Elderly Diabetic Patient: A Case Report, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (11), 811-815. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17622224>

